

#2

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

ACTOR/ROLE IDENTIFICATION (ID)

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Crucial at team-building stage, often at the pre-project stage, and used iteratively throughout project/initiative to revisit/change/rotate roles of actors as necessary.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Used in small, nascent groups, particularly in the pre-funding stage.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No skill required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>30 mins-2 hrs mins (depending on group size & extent of discussion).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Very low, requires basic materials. Can be conducted physically with participants in a room or on an online platform such as Klaxoon, Pinup, or Mural. At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 1, 17, 25, 26.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Photo by Patrick Schneider on Unsplash

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Identify a collection of tasks for completion, and the competencies required to undertake them.
- Understand the interests and capacities of participants in a multi-actor team.
- Identify the roles involved in progressing a team, often at nascent stage / in project proposal stage, when there are little or no resources: Who is good at doing what and who will do what?
- Employ whole-group thinking to the task of creatively and comprehensively envisioning roles.
- Make decisions regarding who will take up what roles in the short, medium and long terms, and whether to rotate/modify/re-allocate roles.
- To assess and revisit what role allocation and to change/adapt if necessary Identify and plan actions to exploit strengths and address weaknesses.

Background and Logic

In nascent stages of interactive innovation project development, the initial core group of actors are challenged with getting it 'off the ground' and, without resources, the core group members must often undertake this work themselves. Work is involved in identifying and recruiting all the appropriate actors who should be involved, researching state of the art, identifying research opportunities, formulating research proposals, and other tasks depending on the focus and nature of the initiatives. In multi-actor groups, a variety of skills, talents, and perspectives are brought together. How can this pool

of diverse capabilities be assessed & exploited? How can roles be allocated in such a way that reflects team members' interests and capabilities, ensuring that they bring the most knowledge available to the project and that they take roles that motivated them? Without roles being allocated equitably and in a way that energises different members of a multi-actor group, group members may lose enthusiasm, and the group may lose 'steam'.

This tool facilitates actors to brainstorm tasks and the competencies required to achieve them successfully. The tool takes a strategic approach to assessing interests and capabilities within a group, allocating roles in a way that leverages the skills, knowledges etc. available to the project. The tool takes into consideration the time and resources available for different group members to commit. It supports decision-making in allocating the roles, and flexibility to revise/rotate roles. It can be used periodically to appraise how members are satisfied with their current roles and make adaptations where necessary. It can be used in conjunction with Tool #1, which would be taken as a first step in mapping actors' different sectoral /professional orientations (actor categories).

Materials

- Flip chart paper
- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers
- Stairs diagram (in how to guide, optional)
- Sellotape
- Match sticks

METHOD / HOW – TO GUIDE

Step 1: Brainstorming Tasks

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the tool/exercise.
- Ask participants to brainstorm tasks for project/initiative development, summarizing the task on a sticky-note (either physically in an in-person meeting or virtually, using an appropriate platform such as Klaxoon, Mural, Pinup etc.)

Liaise with local
press & media

Explore funding
opportunities

Review similar
projects

Organise a
meeting with
local farmers

Step 2: Clustering Tasks into Roles

- Once the brainstorming process is completed, ask participants to cluster similar tasks together/tasks that need a particular skill set (e.g. Information Technology skills or communication skills).
- Once the tasks have been clustered, ask participants to choose a cluster of tasks & present it to the group (allocating roles to participants comes later – this step encourages participants to verbalise/make sense of the clusters).
- After each participant presents a cluster of tasks, facilitate a discussion around the following topics:
- Is the cluster of tasks comprehensive? Do you wish to add another task?
- Do you think that any of the tasks should be moved to another cluster?
- What are the skill sets required to undertake this cluster of tasks?
- What resources (e.g. time) are needed to undertake this cluster of tasks?
- Can the cluster be undertaken by one person, or would it need a team of people?
- Can you allocate a name to this cluster of tasks – what would the role be called?

Image source: Teagasc

Step 3: Allocation/Adoption of Roles

- Allocate 6 matchsticks to participants
- Ask them to place a single or multiple matchsticks on a role to indicate their preferences to undertake that role.
- Once participants have signalled their preference/s to undertake role/s, the popularity of roles is clear from the placing of matchsticks.
- Facilitate a discussion around the following topics:
- Who indicated a preference for this role? Are you willing/available to undertake it?
- Where there are two or more participants wishing to undertake the same role, do you wish to undertake the role jointly, or to rotate the role?
- For how long can you undertake this role before we can as a group revisit the role and see if you need help for anyone?

Step 4: Creating Plans for Roles & Follow-up

- At this point in the process, participants have agreed to take a role, and they can be invited to work alone or as a team (where there are two or more participants working on a task) in the aftermath of the meeting to create a plan of how and when tasks will be undertaken.
- A follow-up meeting should follow where participants present to the wider group their plans for undertaking the role & the tasks involved.
- At subsequent group meetings, the plans and timelines are referred to in assessing progress and aiding decision-making with regard to use of resources (if participants need more help).
- Discussions should facilitate role re-allocation & modification as necessary, in response to changes in project development

